

Rethinking the role of value-added industries for invasive trees in South Africa

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Removal of invasive trees in South Africa is required for climate change adaptation purposes.
- Public funding is insufficient and value-added industries could contribute to land clearing efforts.
- There is a case for bioenergy but the policy environment is not conducive enough.
- Incentives frameworks would be instrumental in supporting private investments.
- Carbon pricing is a promising avenue but its application to invasive trees biomass is complex.
- Impact evaluations of value-added industries on land condition are required to go beyond anecdotal evidence.

SUMMARY

Invasive alien trees are a threat to sustainable development in South Africa due to their rapid propagation and negative impacts on water availability, fire risks, land productivity, and biodiversity conservation. Despite the ambitious three decades-long governmental Working for Water programme to clear and restore land, the problem remains. This paper questions the proposition that value-added industries can contribute to its resolution by providing value to the biomass and supporting upscaled control efforts with private investments. Their financial feasibility remains largely theoretical as most studies resort to *ex ante* assessments untested on the ground and are misleading due to the mix of tangible financial flows and hypothetical environmental benefits. Assumed perverse effects with further propagation remain theoretical or rest on anecdotal evidence. It is suggested that value-added industries and particularly bioenergy hold potential but require a more conducive policy environment. Three priorities are identified: an incentives framework that recognises environmental (dis)services and clarifies potential net carbon gains depending on the accounting system; the provision of updated information to the private sector on resource availability with improved coordination between investors and public programs in charge of land clearing; and innovative supply chain models with improved logistics. Thinking outside the box would help and novel land management options could be considered with natural regrowth and rotations in non-strategic sites, or crop substitution to sustain value chains – which would necessitate strict management rules in exchange for greater flexibility in resource accessibility. Overall, value-added industries for invasive trees encompass climate change adaptation and mitigation and their feasibility depends on their articulation.

Keywords: alien plants, value-added industry, restoration, bioenergy, energy transition

Quel rôle pour les industries de transformation dans la lutte contre les arbres invasifs en Afrique du Sud

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Les plantes invasives exotiques (pin, acacia, eucalyptus) sont une menace en Afrique du Sud en raison de leur propagation rapide et des impacts négatifs sur l'accès à l'eau, les risques de feux, la productivité des terres et la biodiversité. L'ambitieux programme gouvernemental Working for Water mis en oeuvre depuis une trentaine d'années, avec des coupes sur les terres envahies, n'a pas permis de résoudre le problème. J'étudie ici la proposition selon laquelle les industries de transformation peuvent contribuer à ces efforts, en ajoutant de la valeur économique à la biomasse puis en soutenant les efforts d'éradication via des investissements privés supplémentaires. Leur faisabilité financière reste cependant hypothétique car les études sont généralement faites *ex ante* et peu testées en conditions réelles. En outre, elles peuvent être trompeuses car elles mélangent des flux financiers réels et des bénéfices environnementaux plus aléatoires. Les effets pervers annoncés avec la création d'un marché pour la biomasse, et la possible recrudescence des invasions qui s'en suivrait, restent théoriques et anecdotiques. Je suggère que les industries de transformation, et particulièrement les bioénergies, ont un réel potentiel mais nécessitent plus de soutien des politiques publiques. Trois priorités sont identifiées: un cadre incitatif qui reflète les (dis)services environnementaux et contributions nettes en carbone; une information fiable et actualisée concernant les ressources disponibles en biomasse avec une meilleure coordination entre les investisseurs privés et le programme gouvernemental de coupes; des chaînes d'approvisionnement innovatives avec des améliorations logistiques. Le paradigme actuel doit donc être renouvelé et de nouvelles options de gestion des terres proposées notamment avec le recru naturel et des rotations sur les sites peu sensibles, ou la plantation de nouvelles espèces non invasives pour pérenniser l'approvisionnement. Un encadrement plus strict de ces

usages serait alors la contrepartie d'une plus grande flexibilité pour l'accès à la ressource. Au final, le déploiement des industries de transformation des espèces invasives exotiques a un impact sur l'adaptation et l'atténuation du changement climatique et sa faisabilité dépend de leur bonne articulation.

Repensar el papel de las industrias de valor añadido para especies arbóreas invasoras en Sudáfrica

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Las especies de árboles exóticos invasores son una amenaza para el desarrollo sostenible en Sudáfrica debido a su rápida propagación y a sus efectos negativos sobre la disponibilidad de agua, el riesgo de incendios, la productividad de la tierra y la conservación de la biodiversidad. A pesar del ambicioso programa gubernamental de tres décadas de duración *Working for Water*, para la limpieza y restauración de tierras, el problema persiste. Este artículo cuestiona la propuesta de que las industrias de valor añadido pueden contribuir a su resolución aportando valor a la biomasa y apoyando los esfuerzos de control a mayor escala con inversiones privadas. Su viabilidad financiera sigue siendo en gran medida teórica, ya que la mayoría de los estudios recurren a evaluaciones *ex ante* no comprobadas sobre el terreno y son engañosos debido a la mezcla de flujos financieros tangibles y beneficios medioambientales hipotéticos. Los supuestos efectos perversos de una mayor propagación siguen siendo teóricos o se basan en pruebas anecdóticas. Se sugiere que las industrias de valor añadido tienen potencial, en particular la bioenergía, pero requieren un entorno político más propicio. Se identifican tres prioridades: un marco de incentivos que reconozca los servicios o perjuicios medioambientales y aclare las posibles ganancias netas de carbono en función del sistema de contabilidad; el suministro de información actualizada al sector privado sobre la disponibilidad de recursos con una mejor coordinación entre los inversores y los programas públicos encargados del despeje del terreno; y modelos innovadores de cadena de suministro con una logística mejorada. Pensar de manera original ayudaría, como considerar opciones novedosas de gestión de la tierra basadas en regeneración natural y rotaciones en lugares no estratégicos, o la sustitución de cultivos para mantener las cadenas de valor, lo que exigiría normas estrictas de gestión a cambio de una mayor flexibilidad en la accesibilidad a los recursos. En general, las industrias de valor añadido para las especies arbóreas invasoras abarcan la adaptación al cambio climático y la mitigación, y su viabilidad depende de su articulación.

INTRODUCTION

Invasive Alien Plants (IAPs) in South Africa have been identified as a critical threat to biodiversity, water supplies and productive use of land (Everson *et al.* 2014, Holmes 2020, Le Maitre *et al.* 2020, Ndhlovu *et al.* 2011, O'Connor *et al.* 2020). In order to address this problem an ambitious and internationally-praised governmental programme has been in place for almost three decades – Working for Water (WfW) (van Wilgen and Wannenburgh 2016). While it helped the country to slow down the propagation of the main species of IAPs, it is still far from achieving its objectives mainly because of a lack of funding and efficiency in its operations (van Wilgen *et al.* 2022).

Operations implemented by WfW usually include logging and stacking the trees on the site followed by chemical treatments to prevent regrowth, which is required along with repeated removals of seedlings over the years, but without active restoration efforts (Holmes *et al.* 2020). Fire is occasionally used but carries its own risks (i.e. some invasives are stimulated by fires, Fill *et al.* 2017). It remains the exception that the biomass from the invasive trees is subsequently used and processed despite myriad possible end-products (Stafford *et al.* 2018) among which bioenergy stands as a credible candidate in the form of firewood, pellets or based on more sophisticated processes (Hugo 2016). This is significant in a country where unemployment is very high, an economic crisis looms, energy shortages lead to chronic interruptions in electricity supply and an energy transition is necessary as the current system is almost entirely based on coal-fired plants (DMRE 2019).

Sites are invaded at various degrees with implications for the prioritisation of removal activities and their distribution across government programs and the private sector. McConnachie *et al.* (2016: 482) find that “*it would be most effective to focus clearing efforts on sparse rather than densely invaded portions of an infestation [...] Higgins et al. (2001) [...] concluded that clearing strategies that prioritize low-density sites dominated by juvenile alien plants proved to be the most cost effective.*”. These findings suggest that WfW could focus on sparsely invaded areas to prevent propagation while value-added industries could take over in densely invaded areas where most biomass can be supplied at possibly lower costs due to the higher concentration of trees in one site.

This idea of harnessing value-added industries to support efforts to eradicate or at least control IAPs is not novel; it has been discussed and feasibility studies were undertaken to assess its relevance (Hugo 2016), often commissioned by public agencies and departments with a Programme on value-added industries (VAI) expanded since 2002 (Ward *et al.* 2017). Some successful projects are living testaments to the fact that it can be done (Preston 2016) even if some failures also attest to the challenges that lie ahead mostly pointing to the need for localised business models rather than those which favour large-scale production for export markets (Jenkin and Mudombi 2018). Such information has not been systematically collected and analysed, and many statements are likely driven by beliefs and opinions, whereas action is needed urgently in a context where, (i) public spending will remain insufficient and, (ii) the propagation of IAP and the negative impacts they generate continue to increase (van Wilgen *et al.* 2022).

In this article, the rationale and feasibility of developing industrial value chains for the removal of the main IAPs is questioned, namely from the three dominant genera *Acacia*, *Eucalyptus* and *Pinus* (hereafter “invasive trees”). Whether such value chains are feasible and whether they could contribute to the control of the main invasive trees in South Africa are also addressed. A step back is taken in the search for evidence and experience from similar initiatives in other countries and for other species (terrestrial and aquatic animals) that could inform policies in South Africa. This provides the material to analyse how such an issue is studied and what are the questions usually addressed in the literature. Building on interviews with stakeholders, I provide a critical analysis of these issues, identify the questions that must be addressed to go beyond existing knowledge, discuss promising avenues to increase the financial feasibility of VAI and suggest key strategic areas to push the agenda forward.

METHODS

The analysis relies on a review of the literature (grey and peer-reviewed) dedicated to the idea of using VAI for IAP control purposes, and interviews conducted in South Africa to test assumptions on obstacles and enablers. The enablers are then discussed and next steps for a research agenda and knowledge generation are suggested. Interviews were conducted (remote, in-person and email exchanges) with 25 individuals representing governmental bodies related to WfW (n=2) or sustainable land management (n=5), the scientific community (n=6), entrepreneurs in the harvesting and biomass processing sectors (n=7) and NGOs (n=5) with active involvement in restoration, and also took part to meetings and knowledge sharing platforms over the period March-October 2022. These interviews evolved over time to integrate new elements as the analysis unfolded. A previous draft was also circulated to two experts in the field to test the assumptions made and leads proposed, and comments were integrated.

The identification of literature was carried out with Google Scholar using keywords “value-added industry(ies)”, “value-added product”, “invasive”, with various combinations to go beyond the case of South Africa and avoid the limitations of focusing on one country to gather lessons learnt in other contexts. The search was not extended to the use of more general keywords such as “utilisation” in order to keep a reasonable number of references that were assumed to be representative; besides, this study was not meant to be a systematic review and was based on mixed methods. Titles and abstracts were screened to assess relevance with inclusion criteria as follows: explicitly studying the issue of using woody IAP for VAI; not on animals; not only about technologies and technical processes. The snowballing technique and requests to experts and practitioners from the government were also used to make sure key references were not missed; this enabled the identification of key general and review-type publications on terrestrial and aquatic animals with valuable lessons to integrate to the analysis, if only to shine a light on critical differences.

Titles and abstracts were screened to end up with a final selection of 27 documents. References that only mention VAI without providing specific information (cursory references) were excluded.

The sample was analysed using the following variables:

- Approach: Ex post assessment / On-going experiments / Feasibility and prospective studies / Methodologies / Review
- Scope: Supply chain logistics / Biomass requirements & availability / Value-added products volumes / Financial / Socio-economic / Technical on wood properties and suitability / Carbon accounting / Options available / Impacts / General
- IAP: which species involved
- VAI: which type of end-product
- Location
- Obstacles
- Opportunities
- Main conclusions

This first round of analysis allowed the identification of the potential and enablers for VAI to contribute to land restoration. It also provided material to draw some assumptions and prepare interviews to elaborate and explore leads that are thoroughly presented in the Discussion section.

RESULTS

The searches on Google Scholar on 10th of August and 7th of September 2022 yielded the following results:

- “value-added industry” AND “invasive”: 79 hits with 8 relevant references (similar studies and results were subtracted, e.g. when there is both the PhD dissertation and related articles);
- “value-added industries” AND “invasive”: 175 hits, 9 relevant references (once duplicates from previous search were subtracted);
- “value-added product” AND “invasive” AND “South Africa”: 453 hits, 2 relevant references (once duplicates from previous search were subtracted);

The snowballing technique yielded another 8 references (Table 1).

A majority of references collected for this review deal with the feasibility of creating value chains (two-thirds), mostly from a financial point of view but also extending to the socio-economic dimensions and, to a lesser extent, to supply chains logistics, biomass availability and technical feasibility. Cases differ and deal with various types of invasive organisms, and two thirds of collected documents examine cases in South Africa, which may be due in part to the existence of research programs and funding in the context of the governmental Natural Resources Management Programme and the combined contributions of Stellenbosch University and the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), and in

TABLE 1 Results from the literature review

	Approach	Scope	IAP	VAI	Location	Barriers	Opportunities	Conclusions
Vera <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Feas	SCL, Fin, Soc-eco	Acacia, eucalypts, pines	Bioenergy pellets	South Africa (Eastern Cape)	Limited carbon gains when accounting for land use change, high transportation and logistical costs (specific to the location and country)	Real gains on some dimensions (water, employment)	Trade-offs within environmental and socio-economic realms, would need some support justified by environmental services
Dlamani (2020)	Feas	SCL, Fin, tech	Acacia	Building material (wood plastic composites) in townships, specifically ceiling boards	South Africa (Stellenbosch)	Only specific parts of houses (e.g. not exposed to UV radiation)	A circular economy element	Business is feasible at small scale
Felker (2009)	Feas	Tech	Prosopis	Lumber (flooring, high quality furniture)	Global	The species spreading in South Africa are of a non-usable sort	Technically-suitable in original form (e.g. South America), which could be grafted onto the South African sort (genetic improvement)	Great potential and suitability from a technical standpoint
Göswein (2021)	Feas	SCL, Biom, Carbon	Un-tree	Building material (biomass-insulated concrete) in townships (reconstruction and Development Programme) for <i>lighthouse</i>	South Africa (Cape Town)	Large estimated areas of land to be cleared (2,61 – 6,99 Mio ha) to satisfy needs	Avoids burning biomass with positive carbon accounting benefits (best-case ideal scenario goes towards “carbon neutrality at urban scale”)	It offers great potential to achieve near carbon neutral cities and is a favored strategy from a carbon accounting optimisation angle
Marais (2018)	Meth	Tech	Un-tree	Sawlog (lumber), school desk	South Africa	(lack of) accuracy for biomass stocks may be a problem, requires on-site sampling	Recovery for suggested products is a reality, the more products involved the higher the recovery rate, recovery volume assessment methods are feasible yet rudimentary	Better expand the scope of products with lower value ones to maximise recovery rates
Jenkin and Mudombi (2018)	On-going, Feas	SCL, Fin, Soc-eco	Un-tree	Wood pellets for energy (household level)	South Africa	Misaligned government policy, competition from established value chains (e.g. paraffin), high transportation costs, low recovery rate	Must be localised (shorter supply chains, household consumption, local entrepreneurs) to address transportation cost issue with larger-scale facilities	There is a business case for it, and a socio-economic case as well, but government support for localised value chains is required

TABLE 1 Continued

	Approach	Scope	IAP	VAI	Location	Barriers	Opportunities	Conclusions
Melane <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Feas	Fin, Tech	Non-woody IAPs	Electricity	South Africa	High costs related to sub-optimal properties (physical and chemical)	Some plants are suitable	While some plants are suitable, electricity production is at higher cost than with woody plants and residues
Mudavanhu <i>et al.</i> (a) (2017)	Feas	Fin	Acacia <i>saligna</i> (Port Jackson)	Wood polymer Composite	South Africa (Western Cape)	Risks of support to more propagation of invasive trees	GDP contribution, employment, increased tax revenue base	Economically viable, but more robust legal framework that prohibits illegal planting of IAPs is required along private sector co-financing
Mudavanhu <i>et al.</i> (b) (2017)	Feas	Fin	Acacia, eucalypts, pines	Bundle of products: wood chips, firewood, timber, charcoal, briquettes	South Africa (Berg River - Western Cape)	-	Some (not all) scenarios suggest that value chains would be economically sustainable from a cost-benefit perspective including water services	Mixed results
Mudavanhu <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Feas	Fin	Acacia <i>cyclops</i> (Roikraans)	Electricity (gasifiers)	South Africa (De Hoop Nature Reserve - Western Cape)	-	Positive side-effects on electricity availability in-country, reduced carbon emissions	Tends to be economically viable
Petersen <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Feas	Fin, Tech	Un-tree	Aviation fuel	South Africa	-	Diversification to increase economic feasibility, repurposing of crude oil refineries	Hardly economically viable under current conditions
Stafford <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Feas	Biom, Volum	Un-tree	Wood products, wood fuel, electricity	South Africa, Namibia	Carbon losses possible if land use change is considered (e.g. methane from cattle rearing), land cover maintenance required	Carbon gains with energy substitution, which could be monetised to support the value chain	Benefits of removing invasive trees (ecosystem services) outweighs costs of restoration
Stafford <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Feas	Fin	Un-tree	Focus on bioenergy (heat, electricity)	South Africa	Legislative, access and transport costs, secured feedstock	Win-win with ecosystem services and energy for development	Challenging but feasible, microgrids may be most appropriate

TABLE 1 *Continued*

	Approach	Scope	IAP	VAI	Location	Barriers	Opportunities	Conclusions
Stafford and Blignaut (2017)	Feas	Fin	Acacia, eucalypts, pines	Electricity with gasifiers, biochar as co-product	South Africa (Agulhas Plain)	Government must provide support with harvesting operations, follow-up treatments substantial, supplies subject to fire risk and adaptive management is required	Various socio-economic benefits	Financially feasible if there is cost-sharing for biomass supplies between industry and government
Tardivel (2018)	Review, Feas	Option	Plants and animals	All commercial uses	Global, focus on Pacific islands	Perverse effects especially when species dynamics are not fully understood / with incentives to sustain the resource (supplying processing capacities or new cultural norm)	Cost-sharing with private-public partnerships	“Controversial issue” among conservationists; focus on Pacific islands suggests many options around timber and bioenergy
Traynor <i>et al.</i> (2008)	On-going	Soc-eco	Acacia <i>mearnsii</i> (Black Wattle)	Timber processed in South Africa	Swaziland	Overexploitation leading to sub-optimal productivity, threat to grazing	Emergence of middlemen to harvest and transport, which local communities cannot afford especially with collapse of cooperatives; IAP as a real and often under-tapped and under-studied source of livelihoods in rural areas: pulp industry with planting & long term management	Private companies at advantage compared to cooperatives; large demand induced over-exploitation; conflicts among communities regarding IAP management seen as opportunity and threat; overall wattle could be exploited sustainably in the long-run; need to balance benefits of IAP for rural communities and threats due to invasive status
Vundla <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Feas	Fin	Wattle, Acacia Saligna, Pinus, Hakea	Various	South Africa (Eastern Cape)	-	-	Three scenarios: no clearing, business-as-usual, increased clearing with co-financing. Using co-financing and harnessing VAIs would produce positive results overall due to the water and grazing services

TABLE 1 Continued

	Approach	Scope	IAP	VAI	Location	Barriers	Opportunities	Conclusions
Ward <i>et al.</i> (2017)	On-going	Soc-eco	Various tree species	Eco-furniture	South Africa	Governance leading to inefficiencies	Need to go beyond furniture, strengthening Public Private Partnerships, services provided should be factored in to get public funding / support beside market prices	Contrasted opinions on impacts: inefficiencies and high costs, real job creation, failed planning, innovations and training. May contribute to restoration and sustaining WFW. Role of government in promoting an industry is questionable but opens the door to lasting policies.
Bartlett <i>et al.</i> (2018)	On-going	Soc-eco, Tech	Prosopis <i>juliflora</i>	Biochar, poles / fences	India	Lack of capital to purchase larger retorts	Experiments have proven that small-scale production of biochar and living fences is within reach for local communities	Such experiments improve rural livelihoods, and it is expected that it will help eradicating the invasive species
Bole-Rentel <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Feas	Fin, Soc-eco, Tech, Carbon	Un-tree	Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF)	South Africa	Must operate for at least 20 years	Technical potential exists in-country, sugar cane as quickest / cheapest option but IAPs (and garden waste) also appealing with another technology, job opportunities (estimated 100 k direct green jobs and 20 k farm jobs) during 20 years factories' lifetime, opportunities for small / medium enterprises, improvement of balance of trade	A business case exists as the South African SAF could compete with other SAFs (but more expensive than conventional fuel) and even more so with policy support / concessional funding to lower capital costs

TABLE 1 *Continued*

	Approach	Scope	IAP	VAI	Location	Barriers	Opportunities	Conclusions
De Lange <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Feas	Soc-eco	Un-tree	Compressed logs, charcoal, electricity, heat and power	South Africa (Agulhas Plain – Western Cape)	Wildfires (or other disturbances) cause losses to biomass in the short term but densify resource in long-term (dilemma); legal barriers decentralised energy uptake in national grid	Local skills and benefits with more small-scale and decentralised approaches	6 criteria to identify best scenario / technological option: minimal impacts on resource base, job creation, benefits to local people, skills for life, technology performance, cost efficiency. Multicriteria analysis leads to following order: decentralised combined heat and power, compressed logs, pyrolysis for charcoal, gasification for electricity, combustion for electricity
Marais <i>et al.</i> (2001)	On-going, Feas	Fin, soc-econ, Biom	Un-tree	Pulpwood, charcoal, firewood, furniture, garden chips	South Africa	Lack of good quality data at national level	Secondary industries could contribute significantly to development of better management practices for IAPs	Need for better assessments of IAPs volumes, need to identify non-invasive species to replace IAPs once eradicated, need for multi-skilled WfW staff to address VAI, combinations of high and low value products desirable for business resilience
Minatchy <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Ex post	Impact	<i>P. Cattleianum</i> (Guava tree)	Furniture	La Réunion	-	-	Negative impacts due to propagation of other alien species on removal sites; in this specific case with IAPs mixed in tropical forests, development of value chain is not desirable from a conservation standpoint except if specific accompanying measures are implemented

TABLE 1 Continued

Approach	Scope	IAP	VAI	Location	Barriers	Opportunities	Conclusions
Nunez <i>et al.</i> (2012)	General	Animals and fish	Food	Global	Failing to affect invader population size/ expansion, creating a market that needs to be maintained, promoting future invasions, promoting incorporation of invasives into local cultures	Invasive species less susceptible to continuous harvest pressure hence supplies guaranteed	Increasing awareness of invasive species, assisting in early detection and rapid response efforts, boosting local economy
Pasko and Goldberg (2014)	General	All types	Anything	Global	Perverse incentives (rewards for capture of animals and fishes, not at industrial level), property rights, legal issues, population dynamics, local acculturation	In combination with other eradication strategies, outreach, applied to small and distinct populations	A list of favorable (species easily identified, public support, exit strategy...) and unfavorable (isolated environment, no replacement opportunities, low demand...) characteristics are provided to establish feasibility for effective harvest incentive programme
Nega <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Fin, Biom, Volum	<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (Water Hyacinth)	Energy, animal feed and fertilizers	Ethiopia	-	-	Production of biomethane, bioethanol and organic fertilizers is economically viable without subsidies
Verma, R. and S. Suthar (2015)	General	Duckweed (includes 40 species)	Wastewater treatment, bioenergy	Global	Logistics (collection, transport, storage), inconsistent quality and quantity, moisture content	Various associated benefits including alleviation of land use competition between food and bioenergy production	Duckweed technology can be adopted as coupled technology to harness two environmental approaches, i.e. wastewater treatment and energy biomass production

Note: IAP (Invasive Alien Plans), VAI (Value-added industry), Ex post (Ex post assessment), On-going (On-going experiment), Feas (Feasibility and prospective studies), Meth (Methodologies), P-R (peer-reviewed), grey (grey literature), events (workshops, etc.), SCL (Supply chain logistics), Fin (financial), Biom (Biomass requirements & availability), Volum (Value-added products volumes), Soc-eco (socio-economic considerations), Tech (Technical on wood properties, suitability, measurement, industrial processes), Carbon (carbon accounting), Option (options available), Impact (impact on the IAP and/or ecosystems in which it grows), un-tree (unspecified trees)

other part to the choice of keywords (e.g. “value-added industry” rather than “utilisation”). This also explains the prevalence of bioenergy in such studies as South Africa has been facing an energy crisis for a long time. The geographical focus of our sample is also reinforced by the third combination of keywords (see Methods) that explicitly mentions South Africa due to the very high number of hits for “value-added product” AND “invasive”.

Studies are prospective in general, i.e. they look at processes and value chains that remain hypothetical either because the technologies are at the level of Research & Development and have not been tested in real conditions or/and because the use of invasive species was never the main source of raw material. In the latter case, one must be cautious that it is not trivial to change raw material to operate value chains based on proven technologies and existing markets. Indeed, beside differences in terms of properties that may have an impact at the processing level (e.g. calorific value), one must also be attentive to the fact that invasives are by definition unmanaged with implications for the business model: species heterogeneity, varying levels of maturity, contrasted densities between sites, specific modes of access and contracts to access the resource on private and public lands, and others. It matters that feasibility studies tend to overlook such practical constraints that can be expected to significantly affect the results.

The results of these studies are generally (slightly) positive. Yet the lack of experimentation in real conditions is not compensated by satisfactory discussions of the reasons why such value chains, which are said to be feasible, do not materialise. Such reasons usually revolve around the lack of supporting public policies and support to reduce financial risks in a context of high cost of capital, low profit margins and innovation (e.g. Jenkin and Mudombi 2018, Stafford *et al.* 2018), but also missing information on the available stocks (Marais 2018). These aspects generally resort to a policy environment that is not conducive to investments in VAI. Other key obstacles related to the political economy, field conditions and technical issues at the processing stage that impose limitations (e.g. chemical composition) are usually absent from the discussion.

Positive results on financial feasibility also tend to rest on statements around net carbon gains from the processing of invasive species biomass (with associated economic gains), which are presented with little discussion about the conventions and assumptions behind such calculations in the national and international carbon accounting rules (Mudavanhu *et al.* 2016). One exception was provided by Stafford *et al.* (2017) who recognised that such calculations would depend a great deal on the consideration of subsequent land uses. Another important and quite consensual finding across studies is that processing invasive species biomass is a winning economic strategy if (and often, only if) environmental services are factored in the calculations. Yet this is based on rough estimations of such services on a large scale (typically a watershed or administrative unit) and with proxy values and one can question their relevance at a finer scale once specific field conditions are fully acknowledged.

Only five studies were found dealing with on-going experiments and another one presenting an ex-post assessment. Their lessons are useful and balanced (feasible, room for improvement, identification of the weaknesses) but may remain incomplete because they are based on anecdotal evidence and fail to address replication, e.g. Lewis *et al.* (2020) who present a success story (without much evidence) of processing a brown seaweed (Wakame) to develop a circular economy, reduce chemical products pollution and reduce the threats to local mussels. Besides, they are generally focused on the financial and socio-economic aspects and do not provide a long-term assessment neither address the impact of such value-added industries on the eradication or control of the resource. On the latter aspect, the only available evidence applies to the shifting cultural norms that result from the creation of novel value chains rather than perverse incentives for an industry to prevent the eradication of the feedstock. Note that this applies mostly to terrestrial and aquatic animals (Pasko and Goldberg 2014) along the lines of the “to eat or not to eat” question (Nunez *et al.* 2012).

DISCUSSION

The apparent contradiction: a self-defeating strategy?

A contradiction might arise when a profitable activity is created based on a resource that is targeted for eradication, leading to conflicting goals. While this hypothesis does not appear frequently in the literature dedicated to the use of woody invasive plants, it has been a vibrant topic of discussion in the case of animals. In these latter cases, this argument is usually proven by experience as exemplified by the cases of rats and snakes in India when rewards are provided for capture, and incentives are thus indirectly provided to local populations to sustain the resource when the costs involved remain low (Pasko *et al.* 2014). Other examples exist where the pressure of the industry for species like brown trout in New Zealand or red deer in Patagonia is high and makes it unlikely that it will be eradicated (Nuñez *et al.* 2012). The argument is also solid when built around the incorporation of invasives into local cultures, such as for wild boar in Hawaii or wild horses in the American Southwest (Ibid).

It is the contention of this paper that the latter argument could be applied to tree species in South Africa especially when they were introduced to provide fodder and shade (case of *Prosopis* species in Northern Cape – Wise *et al.* 2012) but also as they constitute a source of livelihoods and provide other services such as fuelwood, medicines and fruits (Shackleton and Shackleton 2012). Yet such cases do not involve value chains established at industrial scale.

More generally, the fact that the risk (and its associated evidence) is discussed mostly in the case of animals may be an indication of its limited relevance for the case of invasive trees in South Africa. While Nuñez *et al.* (2012) suggest that the reasoning may apply to the forestry industry, such a statement is unconvincing because it touches upon another (admittedly related) process whereby such invasive trees

would be planted by forestry companies and become invasive when they escape. It is undeniable that the forest sector has played a central role in the introduction and propagation of invasive trees in South Africa (van Wilgen and Richardson 2012), but this trajectory is evolving within a strict regulatory framework that remains to be fully enforced. Furthermore, encouraging propagation is unlikely to be an intentional strategy as the sector relies exclusively on its own intensively managed plantation estate.

Other distinctive features make lessons from animals of limited transferability. First, population dynamics differ as well as the environment in which these species propagate. The capacity for animals to move around makes them more difficult to control: e.g., it makes little sense to clear specific areas of the ocean from lionfish if they remain in adjacent zones because it is practically impossible to prevent their migrations, and reproduction somewhere will lead to renewed infestation in other places. While one may argue that a similar phenomenon exists with seeds, as removing trees does not prevent remaining seeds to germinate at a later period and seeds can move long distances quickly, a given area can be monitored and a successful restoration is likely to improve resilience against new invasions.

The other distinctive feature is that the propagation of invasive trees can in theory be treated and monitored much more easily and efficiently than with animals. As evidence shows, when most of the invasive trees in South Africa are only cut down without further active treatment, restoration or monitoring, then the benefit is limited (Holmes *et al.* 2020, van Wilgen *et al.* 2012). Most of the time the sites are colonised with young invasive trees just one or two years later and the operations must be repeated. But with the will and resources to tackle such risks, solutions exist (e.g. application of herbicides repeated removal of seedlings in subsequent years, biological control) that require more spending to be factored in cost calculations. The value-added industries that benefit from free access to the resource should be compelled to handle such operations or cover such costs, admittedly at the expense of their financial feasibility. In addition to field verifications managed by the public bodies when governmental programmes are involved and/or clearing is required by law, certification schemes also have a complementary role to play as exemplified by the interest expressed by the Forest Stewardship Council in this instance (FSC 2021).

A more general counterargument to the perverse effect of using value-added industries to control invasive trees is that the resource is so vast, and still untapped, that it is very unlikely to be exhausted with or without value-added industries. This is especially true because of rapid spread rates of 7–15% per year (Kotzé *et al.* 2010, Le Maitre *et al.* 2002). True, the resource is distributed across sites that imply varying costs of access because of distance, road infrastructure, topography and other factors (Hugo 2016). All the resource is thus not economically accessible and attractive for value-added industries, which may have incentives to make sure that the best sites remain productive and accessible over time. This in turn gives credit to the risk of poor post-harvest treatments and lack of investments into ecosystem restoration. But this is

manageable in different ways: processing capacities can usually move around to create as much value as possible near or on the harvesting sites (e.g. chippers and pelletizers – interviews), and average costs could be considered when studying the financial feasibility of the investment projects.

Another reason to challenge the apparent contradiction is that exit strategies could be designed upfront to manage such uncertainties. With proper and reliable assessments of the biomass available and the associated access costs, the lifetime of the projects can be adjusted to the feedstocks and the appropriate technologies can be selected for which profitability is achievable with such time frames (about 10 years for heating systems based on chips and a feasibility radius of about 100 km for biomass supplies – interviews). Moreover, permits to establish processing capacities can be delivered according to the supply base, as was stipulated by law in Indonesia in the case of the pulp and paper industry – the processing capacities had to be aligned with the size of tree plantation concessions to avoid incentives to venture into protected forest areas (Pirard 2010).

It is reasonable to think that large-scale capacity projects would not be the most appropriate in this context and that flexibility and relatively limited capital investments would be necessary to prevent lock-in effect. Besides, such flexibility could also translate into the degree of capital recycling by tweaking the technological processes to accommodate other uses and/or feedstock as exemplified with coal-fired plants that can also process biomass with co-firing, and where biomass could then be replaced again by coal if biomass becomes unavailable due to successful eradication of invasive trees. Alternatively, other climate-resilient and biodiversity-friendly crops could be cultivated to keep operating the industry and adding value to infested marginal lands (Baral *et al.* 2022).

Positive cost-benefit analyses are misleading because of intangible benefits and hidden costs

The economic analysis of the removal and processing of invasive trees by value-added industries can be done in at least two very different ways. First, it can be restricted to the financial aspects of the business to estimate the financial feasibility. Results suggest it is challenging: profits could materialise (Bole-Rentel *et al.* 2022, Dlamani 2020, Stafford *et al.* 2018) but may require product diversification and technological improvements (Petersen *et al.* 2022), which usually calls for some sort of government support (Jenkin and Mudombi 2018, Stafford and Blignaut 2017). Recommendations push towards small scale capacities with limited upfront investments as opposed to establishing large-scale capacities that require the retention of sizeable amounts of assets and depend on a large and secure source of feedstock (Stafford *et al.* 2018). Economies of scale are not addressed explicitly but the implicit argument is that agility and flexibility are desirable if not necessary.

Second, the calculations can rely on the application of the cost benefit analysis framework which goes beyond financial aspects and integrates all sorts of environmental services. For instance, it integrates the gains in terms of water supplies and

biodiversity conservation, of which most are not priced by the market. These cost benefit analyses are mostly positive and make a case in favour of removing alien trees with further processing (Mudavanhu *et al.* 2016, Mudavanhu *et al.* 2017 b, Vundla *et al.* 2016). But their positive results are largely due to intangible benefits not associated with cash flows whereas the costs are tangible as investors must pay the bills to operate their plants. This major difference between financial and economic analyses must be fully understood as it has fundamental implications for the feasibility of the value-added industries (see section on “Creating an enabling environment (1)”).

Another important aspect of available analyses, both financial or economic, is that they are prospective and rely on assumptions usually untested on the ground and/or at scale. In doing so they tend to rely on inaccurate, hence misleading proxy figures for supply costs due to a lack of studies. Two examples illustrate this flaw: the study by Stafford and Blignaut (2017) on the potential for electricity generation in the Agulhas plain and the Imperial (2021) report on optimal supply chains for Sustainable Aviation Fuel. Both pay minimal attention to such costs estimations, which lack transparency and sensitivity analyses. Such average values are questionable and could change results. For instance, a report was released to fill this knowledge gap and concludes: “*there is a significant cost range for the preparation and harvesting [. . .] alternative sites will need to be studied to capture a range of tree sizes, stem counts, canopy densities, species and potential products*” (Shuttleworth and Ackerman 2009: 36–37).

Invaded areas are by definition unmanaged, as opposed to tree plantations, so that supply costs differ to a large extent at least in their structure. Varying densities depending on sites, with uneven levels of maturity and age within each site, mixed species within and/or between sites, only one rotation with implications for logging roads and skid trails investments, are all aspects that make the supply and processing costs higher than in plantations. But the magnitude of these additional costs compared to plantation operations remains undocumented yet significant (interviews). This matters because it could as well be balanced with the gains from not investing into the establishment of plantations or its management, which is usually considered as one of the main reasons for a lack of investments into tree plantations worldwide with considerable time lag between investments and revenues and difficult access to reasonably priced loans (Barua *et al.* 2014). In the end, it is not clear whether supply costs would eventually be higher or lower compared to intensively managed plantations, and even less so what would be the magnitude of the difference.

Studies about the financial feasibility of VAI miss a variety of hidden costs that relate to the realm of transaction costs. Operations hardly unfold as planned and many frictions emerge on the ground especially when multiple landowners are involved (van Kooten *et al.* 2002). These tend to be proportional to the number of actors involved (Gregersen *et al.* 2010, Lapeyre *et al.* 2015), which is expected to be high in a context where small-scale operations and job creation are favoured (Turpie *et al.* 2008). Apart from the many incidents taking place in a supply chain (such as equipment breaking

down, or heavy rains preventing access to harvesting sites), the fluidity of the feedstock supply is more at risk for invasive trees because the resource is located on many different and unmanaged sites, with various tenure and harvest arrangements and reliance on the capacity of the public authorities to give access or make deals with farmers. For instance, anecdotal evidence says about 20% of sites are inaccessible for various reasons (interviews). Last, issues related to availability of skilled labour and training requirements, access to capital for activities that take place almost in a grey area (compared to commercial plantations), and overall lack of business support may play a decisive role in the feasibility of innovative value chains.

The hidden costs problem in South Africa is also compounded by the history of the country and the politics that create at least two sources of division: between the national and provincial levels (and particularly the Western Cape with a political leadership at odds with the national government), and between the business and political elites that lack a trust relationship (interviews). Another two layers could be added: the lobbying of the coal industry (as a competitor to the bio-energy sector) which is powerful and carries very high stakes in terms of poverty alleviation and rural development (WRI 2021), and endemic corruption as recently substantiated by the reports from the Judicial Commission of Inquiry into Allegations of State Capture (<https://www.statecapture.org.za/>). These hard truths, albeit difficult to assess quantitatively, can be assumed to have significant implications on the ease of doing business for the value-added industries and may hamper their upscaling if not addressed.

These findings are in line with the conclusions presented in van Wilgen and Wilson (2018) based on a few scenarios of invasive plant control developed by ASSET Research. They point to the fact that estimates of the financial viability of land clearing operations that involve the commercialisation of value-added products depend on several assumptions such as accurate estimates of invaded areas, reasonable costs, or compensations for environmental services, among others. However, they indicate that accurate estimates of these variables are seldom available.

A portfolio of land management options to manage trade-offs?

The general assumption is that the removal of invasive trees is part of programmes that aim at their eradication, or at least control, and that land clearing is followed by ecosystem restoration. Yet not only this has not been the case (van Wilgen *et al.* 2022), but one may question if restoration is relevant for at least three reasons: (i) costs involved are significant (Ibid), which in turn leads to failure even to attempt restoration, (ii) the feasibility of new value chains would be enhanced with the continuous supply of raw material from rotations (regrowth or crop substitution), and (iii) invasive trees have also economic uses and values for local communities under certain circumstances so that it may be relevant to question their reduction to sustainably low levels in regions where poverty and unemployment are prevalent and where they

contribute to local livelihoods (Shackleton *et al.* 2007, Shackleton and Shackleton 2018).

McConnachie *et al.* (2016: 481) conclude, based on their assessment of the cost-effectiveness of WfW: “*This highlights the need to focus scarce resources on priority areas, so that available funds can be more effectively utilized. Currently, there is a lack of focus that leads to the dilution of funding, with the inevitable consequence that not enough projects are making adequate progress*”. This statement is reinforced by van Wilgen *et al.* (2022) who recommend considering triage, i.e. focussing resources wherever it is the most relevant from an invasive plants control perspective. Therefore, this study argues that it is relevant to explore various land management options that would suit various contexts depending on factors, e.g. the amount of environmental services to be provided, the costs involved, or the needs either for local livelihoods or to supply processing industries.

Five main complementary land management options are proposed for their consideration in debates about the control of invasive trees:

- Option 1: Trees are removed and the land is subsequently restored to its original ecosystem state; biomass utilisation is a one-off and substantial efforts are invested into ecosystem restoration with the provision of many environmental services (note: a possible variation is post-removal treatment to prevent regrowth but without active restoration efforts);
- Option 2: Trees are removed and there is no post-removal treatment, which leads to re-invasion; a second round of removal and utilisation can take place several years later and more in the future; environmental services are minimal and provided for short periods of time with potential further damage to the ecosystems depending on the type of harvesting operations (e.g. FSC certified or not);
- Option 3: Trees are removed and the land is subsequently put to a productive use involving crops and/or livestock with mixed consequences on local livelihoods (depends on practises by local communities, e.g. firewood and shade) but expected positive consequences

on economic outputs; implications for environmental services may be highly dependent on the land and types of productive uses;

- Option 4: Trees are removed and other biodiversity-friendly (indigenous) and climate-resilient trees or bushes are substituted in order to maintain the raw material supplies to the newly created value chains; this option may be a compromise between productive uses, sustained local value chains, eradication of invasive trees, and environmental services provision.
- Option 5: The “do-nothing” option could be part of the mix when access is difficult, site characteristics are not conducive to productive uses, and dis(services) caused by invasive trees are not significant. This “do-nothing” approach applies to formal activities – value chains, land clearing and restoration – and does not exclude informal local exploitation to sustain livelihoods.

Option 4 remains absent from the discussions, yet it could solve problems associated with logistics and the “moving target” problem, as well as the risk of creating perverse incentives to not eradicate the invasive trees in the intervention area. The related option 2 that allows invasive trees to regenerate for future rotations has also been absent from discussions for a good reason: it does not contribute directly to the eradication of invasive trees. But as only a fraction of invaded lands can be restored then a portfolio of options would provide a more pragmatic approach; furthermore, the economic value created with this long-term use could be partially spent on other sites for restoration purposes, e.g. via an earmarked contribution.

The relevance and desirability of any of the five options is likely to be site-specific to a large extent so that scientifically sound assessments are required to allocate land across options. While water and biodiversity have been popular criteria to justify interventions, it was found that “*Over a quarter of the control [by WfW] was not in priority areas for biodiversity and/or water conservation*” (van Wilgen *et al.* 2022: 1) and that “*there are many high priority catchments which are not receiving any funding and low priority catchments which are receiving substantial allocations*” (Forsyth

TABLE 2 *Main characteristics of the four land management options for invaded land*

Land Management Options	Removal of invasive trees	Post-removal treatments	Restoration to original ecosystem state	Natural regrowth of invasive trees and rotation system	Productive use of land post-removal (agriculture, livestock)	Substitution of invasive trees by alternative crops to supply integrated value chains
Option 1	X	X	X			
Option 2	X			X		
Option 3	X				X	
Option 4	X					X
Option 5 (“do-nothing”)	May include informal harvesting					

et al. 2012: 51). There is thus considerable room for improvement in site-prioritisation, which may depend on the assessment of at least three critical dimensions:

- Feasibility:
 - o Financial feasibility. Each of the options must be assessed against the costs associated with the activities involved: land clearing, restoration, biomass supply chain (including with new crops for continuous supplies), infrastructure investments, alternative productive uses (e.g. farming), permit issuance, etc. These costs may be highly dependent on characteristics such as land fertility and location / access.
 - o Legal feasibility. South Africa has a comprehensive set of laws and regulations with respect to the management of invasive species that, despite weak law enforcement, indicates what management options are possible depending on tenure and other variables (e.g. some invasive species may not be utilised or traded according to law).
- Environmental (dis)services. These refer to water services, carbon sequestration, biodiversity conservation, agriculture and grazing land productivity, fire management, and others.
- Livelihoods. It is often taken for granted that invasive trees cause negative externalities but it is also important to acknowledge their contributions to the livelihoods of communities in some instances. This aspect complicates the assessment and may downplay some arguments and decisions in favour of the control of invasive trees.

Interesting attempts of site prioritisation were made in the past, e.g. Forsyth *et al.* (2012) used a multi-criteria analysis to identify priority quaternary catchments in the Western Cape Province. Their results were used by the provincial government to guide their own interventions and two of the authors were part of the team doing the prioritization work. Yet, our consideration of five land management options versus the binary choice made by WfW between areas treated and not treated, makes the process more complicated and will require further research to decide on the applied methods.

Creating an enabling environment (1): setting the incentives right and sharing the costs

Because the current conditions in South Africa are such that the financial feasibility of value-added industries remains to be demonstrated at scale and in practice, a more enabling environment would correct a would-be market failure when the biomass is not given any added value.

Depending on the land management options, various services are provided to a diversity of beneficiaries: e.g. city-dwellers or farmers with increased access to water, tourism operators with restored landscapes for wildlife economies, local populations with enhanced biodiversity and associated products, large-scale farmers with higher land productivity,

worldwide population with reduced carbon losses due to fewer fires and energy substitution. But the question remains how to transfer such benefits to VAI. Several options exist with varying levels of development in South Africa.

For instance, the Department of Environmental Affairs and Development Planning of the Western Cape province has explored the feasibility of using economic policy instruments, specifically an Alien Clearing Water Charge (DEA DP 2018) with a payment by the water service authority (in the relevant municipalities) to landowners for clearing and maintenance. This scheme was not implemented for several reasons, such as the uncertainties regarding the legality for a given municipality to pay for activities located outside of its boundaries (e.g. upstream water catchments supplying municipal areas downstream), or increased inequality in terms of water payments due to free water provided to a portion of the water users (interviews). But there is a political will to pursue the examination of such avenues for financial transfers either to landowners, harvesting operators or VAI, and a guide was released in this respect (Mander and Mander 2021). The water payment scheme is similar to other Payments for Water Services that have come to fruition in other countries with proven feasibility (e.g. Pirard 2012).

Another interesting attempt for such transfers is the certification of environmental services by a leading forestry standard – the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC). While this standard is focused on natural forest management with a strong presence in tropical countries, it has been diversifying towards environmental services in the form of “claims” (rather than offsets or credits) paid for by private companies as part of their ESG (Environmental Social Governance) policies (FSC 2021). There is at least one application to the removal of invasive trees in South Africa (SGS 2020), which attests to its relevance even though two barriers to more systematic application are identified: the forest management condition may not be met for the clearing of non-forest ecosystems such as fynbos or grasslands, and the transaction costs might be disincentivizing and possibly even annihilate the expected gains from selling “claims”. FSC certification is also one element that may improve the attractiveness of value-added products for export markets, as is the case with a South African producer that ships certified pellets to Europe (interviews, see section on “The carbon accounting issue”).

Public support is already happening as harvesting operations are commonly paid for by the government through WfW, or owing to other government-sponsored operations such as the LandCare programme which makes deals with farmers to clear their land. But the situation remains poorly organised and many deals seem far too opportunistic to be able to reconcile the interests of all parties: government to solve pressing environmental problems, landowners to meet their legal requirements with respect to removing invasive trees, harvesters to operate on the easiest sites, and VAI to access the biomass at the lowest costs. Therefore, while it happens that VAI could in theory benefit from such programmes (e.g. by sharing the cost burden as proposed in Stafford and Blignaut 2017), this system has significant potential for improvement with better coordination (see next section).

Overall, setting an incentives framework faces two challenges: (i) benefits in terms of environmental services but also other contributions to the economy may occur in parallel with losses for other stakeholders (e.g. lost access to the resource by poor population groups) so that incentives provided to some stakeholders might lead to inequitable outcomes and distribution of benefits leading to conflicts, and (ii) benefits (or losses) are only estimated in relative terms so that the reference situation is key as a point of comparison but one that may be difficult to agree on. These two challenges are illustrated by Figure 1, considering that the results are indicative only. Besides, the distribution of benefits and losses across a diversity of stakeholders is also missing at this stage and would depend on sites. Therefore Figure 1 is not based on quantified results and proportions are not intended to reflect the real situation, just directions.

It is stressed that these benefits and losses are by essence relative and depend on the scenario chosen as the point of reference. This scenario is also called a “counterfactual” and describes the most likely situation in the absence of the incentive being provided; it is the cornerstone of any sound impact evaluation as explained by McConnachie *et al.* (2016) in their application to WfW. For example, if a value-added industry invests in the harvesting of invasive trees and applies post-removal treatments to prevent regrowth, should it be assessed against a “do-nothing” scenario with no removal whatsoever (due to poor law enforcement and lack of funding) or against

a “removal” scenario (due to common practices by WfW), or any other one? The determination of the reference scenario / counterfactual is thus a critical input for the evaluation of impacts and, in turn, to justify the delivery of incentives.

This issue has been thoroughly debated in the related field of avoided deforestation for reducing CO₂ emissions based on international money transfers, which also requires the setting of counterfactual scenarios with a variety of possible methods (e.g. Combes Motel *et al.* 2009) but large potential for loopholes (e.g. Cuenca *et al.* 2018). This aspect is important because the reference scenario (and the resulting assessed benefits or losses of a given course of action) will determine the extent of required incentives and their justification. This is further illustrated by the thorny case of carbon accounting discussed in the related section.

Creating an enabling environment (2): sharing strategic information and optimising logistics

Apart from the various incentives described in the previous section, two main avenues for enhanced feasibility are identified: strategic information availability and optimised logistics. First, despite previous efforts to map invasive trees in South Africa (e.g. Holden *et al.* 2021, Kotzé *et al.* 2010), information on their location, density, species and biomass available for various types of products remains uncertain and scarce. In fact, any investor pondering the feasibility of developing a

FIGURE 1 Indicative costs, benefits and losses for various scenarios

Note: “Do-nothing” scenario means that no action whatsoever is taken on the invaded sites; “Removal” scenario means that trees are cut down and left on site; “Removal+” scenario means that trees are cut down and post-harvest treatments are applied such as herbicides and repeated seedlings removal in subsequent years to prevent regrowth; “VAI” scenario means that biomass from logged trees is processed into value-added products for marketing. Benefits / losses for each scenario (or combinations of scenario) are broken down in up to 8 categories and indicative trends are provided when two scenario are compared (e.g. the “Removal” scenario provides likely benefits for water supplies and likely losses for above-ground carbon compared to the “Do-nothing” scenario). Note that the columns respectively for costs and benefits / losses associated to scenario are represented on different scales and are not comparable.

business based on the processing of invasive trees would struggle to know how much biomass is accessible and at what costs, which in turn depends on many biophysical factors such as proximity to the road network and steepness of slopes, type and density of trees, among others (e.g. Hugo 2016, Stafford and Blignaut 2017). In addition, other aspects can be expected to have a significant impact on supply costs such as tenure, willingness to cooperate by landowners, or coordination with WfW to collect biomass on site after land clearing is completed.

Such information management lags far behind needs despite an attempt to fill the gap with the BioEnergy Atlas (Hugo 2016, <https://bea.saeon.ac.za/>) designed and coordinated by the South African Environmental Observatory Network (SAEON). This Atlas was launched in 2016 with financial support from the Department of Science and Innovation (DSI) to disseminate strategic information about biomass availability and uses to all stakeholders. It contains valuable data and information on aspects such as infrastructure and markets, processing capacities and biomass availability, feasibility studies and contact details for a variety of actors. Yet it could still be improved with more comprehensive information that meets the stated needs of the private sector (e.g. more detailed technology descriptions with implications for the relative costs of bioenergy options – interviews), and even more critically with improved and frequently updated maps and biomass assessments. Besides, the BioEnergy Atlas, for all the valuable information it contains and its user-friendly interface, remains under-utilised probably because of lack of active promotion among business circles.

A second area of improvement is logistics, which are usually mentioned as a major issue where inefficiencies abound (interviews). In this context, logistics refers not only to transport costs but also the integration of value chains with a variety of products (including soil-enhancement for agriculture: biochar, mulch, woody vinegar), the optimization of flows of resource and the use of residues, coordination between processors and WfW regarding biomass availability, the pooling of resources (e.g. transport), moving processing capacities around and providing as much value on site as possible (e.g. chipping and pelletizing), and other dimensions. Logistics have always been an obstacle to investments and development in many parts of the African continent, with dire impacts on the agricultural sector and the prosperity of farmers (Collier and Dercon 2014). This is also illustrated by the fact that most successful start-ups in the region tend to be in the logistics business (The Economist 2022). It seems plausible that substantial gains could thus be made to increase the competitiveness of VAI that rely on an unmanaged resource, which go far beyond logistical issues faced by the forestry sector that actively manages its own plantation estates.

The carbon accounting issue: a tale of two paradigms

Depending on the results, carbon accounting could make a difference to the financial feasibility of VAI, either with carbon credits, relative competitiveness compared to fossil fuels with carbon tax exemptions, or various types of support

with impact investing or certification to access markets (e.g. with the implementation of a border tax adjustment in the European Union). This section discusses the two paradigms, or guiding principles, that could be adopted and that lead to opposite results with either net carbon losses or gains: one assumes that invasive trees are harvested for processing purposes (possibly with associated land restoration), and the other one views (“waste”) biomass as a by-product of land clearing operations that aim primarily at invasive alien plant control.

Indeed, in the former case cutting down the trees equates to losing the above-ground carbon stored in the wood, especially if the biomass is then burned and processed into energy as opposed to being stored more permanently in furniture. This is even more acute in a context where planting trees to sequester carbon and compensate carbon emissions elsewhere is praised and translates into large-scale initiatives to reforest or even afforest land (Irwin 2020) despite warnings by scientists about the threats to grassland ecosystems (Bond *et al.* 2019) and the balancing role of soil organic carbon (e.g. Zhou *et al.* 2022 for the case of savanna ecosystems). In such a case carbon accounting is deceptive and would not easily be turned into a case for funding for bioenergy; it could actually be the contrary.

In the latter case, though, the perspective is reversed because it is assumed that the biomass is already made available and VAI are not responsible for the cut; this paradigm is justified by several legal and environmental considerations. Invasive trees in South Africa must be removed by law and the restoration of ecosystems is assumed to be a very effective climate change adaptation strategy at least from a water management perspective (Le Maitre *et al.* 2002). This is in itself a sufficient justification for clearing and restoration, and the main reason why only about 15% of invaded areas were treated since the beginning of the WfW programme is very likely a lack of funding (and some inefficiencies in the use of the available budget as well) and failed law enforcement.

It ensues from such a paradigm that processing the biomass enables avoidance of methane and CO₂ emissions that would be released from the decaying or burnt biomass left on site. Furthermore, the substitution of coal-based power generation by bioenergy equates to reducing emissions from the energy sector. This rationale can be summarized as follows: first invasive trees are removed for climate change adaptation purposes because ecosystems must be preserved from such invasions and restored. Then the biomass available on site is either left decaying (or burning) and releasing Greenhouse Gases (GhG, or processed into products including bioenergy that substitutes coal for climate change mitigation purposes. The acceptance and validity of such a paradigm depends on what qualifies as the business-as-usual scenario. In other words: would harvesting be done without the VAI as a market for the feedstock? This is a point that remains to be decided for the application of the newly released VERRA methodology for the use of biochar from waste biomass and issuance of carbon credits, as the characterisation of “waste biomass” remains disputed in our case (interviews, <https://verra.org/methodologies/methodology-for-biochar-utilization-in-soil-and-non-soil-applications/>).

This is a difficult and complex issue which can be viewed as a chicken and egg problem: is increased removal justified by the new demand by the industry, or is the industry created in response to these new feedstock opportunities? The reality can be even more complex and the truth could well be in the middle: is there a broad strategy to put forces in common and pursue several objectives at the same time (adaptation to climate change and energy substitution) in a planned fashion? These are not trivial questions because the answer determines whether invasive trees removal should be considered as a business-as-usual scenario, which in turn determines if land use change emissions (mostly the release of above-ground carbon stocks) should be attributed to bioenergy. If it is the case, calculations would lead to net emissions and one might conclude that this is a self-defeating situation where the necessity to eradicate invasive trees and the environmental gains it provides is not acknowledged and the option of getting support from VAI is dismissed from a climate change mitigation point of view.

This discussion is illustrated by an on-going flagship bioenergy project in the province of Eastern Cape (Vera *et al.* 2022). A pellet factory running on sawmill residues went bankrupt and was taken over in 2019 by a South-African–Dutch consortium with support from the Dutch government. The plan is to use invasive trees as the main source of feedstock for woodchips and pellet production with a start in August 2023. Production will initially be exported to Europe to substitute coal. This marketing will take place in the framework of the European Renewable Energy Directive that provides incentives for renewable energies: if bioenergy is considered carbon neutral then it can outcompete coal due to carbon pricing. This will be the case as pellets and woodchips are certified by SBP (Sustainable Bioenergy Program) due to the legal requirements to remove invasive trees.

It is particularly interesting that these pellets are not processed in-country to replace coal in the context of the energy transition and commitments made by South Africa in the wake of the Paris Agreement in 2015 as part of the Climate Change Convention (UNFCCC). The reason lies at least partly with the lack of an enabling environment: South Africa has not put in place a high enough carbon price so far for bioenergy produced out of invasive trees can compete with coal (note that CO₂ emissions from road transport to Mpumalanga province where coal-fired plants are concentrated are estimated to be broadly equivalent to shipping to The Netherlands – Vera *et al.* 2022; but they would be much lower if the wood is sourced from nearby infested sites). As it stands the carbon price is USD 9.2 per tCO₂e (World Bank 2022), and the break-even price remains to be calculated that would make such bioenergy more competitive for the benefit of the just energy transition.

Note that the Climate Bill under discussion in South Africa plans to have progressive increases to USD 30 per tCO₂e by 2030. Admittedly, this policy would push energy prices upward and to the detriment of the competitiveness of the South African economy (or energy prices would be subsidized, which equally affects the economy in the long-run due to the public spending involved) but two counter-arguments

can be made. First, the country has made commitments as part of the Paris Agreement and is engaged in an energy transition with progressive de-phasing of coal-fired plants, so that the carbon tax would only speed up the process by increasing the competitiveness of alternative energy sources. Second, as coal is condemned in the long term due to its sizeable contribution to GhG emissions, it is preferable for the country to anticipate such turning point by unleashing investments and innovations in the alternative sources of energy.

CONCLUSIONS: TOWARDS A RESEARCH AGENDA

The initial question posed was whether VAI could provide support to the removal of invasive trees in South Africa, and it was answered through a combination of literature review and interviews to substantiate the analysis, identify gaps and suggest new directions. Several salient points arose: (i) evidence of feasibility at scale is still lacking as studies are mostly prospective and their assumptions remain largely untested on the ground, (ii) perverse effects (maintained or stimulated invasions either for the purpose of ensuring a permanent feedstock or because of unintended ecological effects of harvesting operations) do not go beyond statements or anecdotal evidence (as opposed to terrestrial and aquatic animals), (iii) existing cost benefit studies tend to be positive but depend to a large extent on the inclusion of environmental services that do not translate into cash flows for the operators, (iv) incentives frameworks are thus required but difficult to design due to the variety of services involved, their variability with site characteristics, the difficult choices of counterfactual scenarios for comparison, among others, (v) the policy environment does not support the emergence of VAI but could still be improved to increase financial support (e.g. carbon tax, sharing the burden of supply costs) and provide in-kind regulatory support (e.g. facilitating access, enforcing existing regulations on mandatory clearing, providing infrastructure); overall the lessons from the vibrant charcoal industry in Namibia, based on biomass from invasive encroacher bushes, are inspirational with coordinated regulations across ministries, a dense network of stakeholders and a balanced set of policies for economic value creation and sustainable land management (Kayambazinthu and Oeba 2019), (vi) avenues to boost private sector investments with better profit prospects are also believed to include the creation and sharing of strategic and updated information on biomass availability as well as innovations to optimise logistics, all of which could be part of the establishment of a business acceleration model.

The outcome of the analysis can be translated into a research agenda to create the evidence base and to provide the means to move forward with the contribution of VAI whenever desirable. Firstly, the existing focus on prospective studies should be compensated by the systematic analysis of the wealth of experience with past and on-going VAI in South Africa to identify factors of success and failure. Secondly, impact evaluations would be obvious candidates to test if VAI hold the potential to provide a significant contribution to the fight against invasive trees or if they either create perverse

incentives to renew the resource or lead to more degradation (e.g. due to use of heavy equipment or stimulation of pioneer species). Thirdly, the contribution of Water Funds as mechanisms to organise and fund land clearing operations and the role they allocate to VAI needs to be thoroughly studied and lessons learned because it remains to date one of the most credible and promising ways to support action in this space; the case of the Greater Cape Town Water Fund is eloquent in this regard with sizeable operations and a Decision Support System to monitor impacts and support planning. This could be complemented by analytical efforts to link the incentives framework to the Just Energy Transition Partnership, either for mobilizing additional financial resources (concessional loans and/or Foreign Direct Investment) or supporting conducive policies (e.g. higher carbon tax) or both, also seem relevant leads to pursue in the short term. Fourthly, this is related to another fertile and much needed research avenue on the contributions to climate change mitigation and adaptation, considering that securing water supplies has been a focus to justify action by the government (beside job creation). This speaks to carbon accounting rules that vary and evolve, the attribution of causality to harvesting leading to biomass supplies and processing, the lack of significant carbon pricing in the South African context, but also a better understanding of the carbon dynamics associated with land management options. Fifthly, supply chain models hold potential for increased efficiencies and research contributions could include innovative logistics for harvesting and transport, more accurate and updated models of invaded areas with species and biomass volumes, as well as tools to centralise and disseminate such strategic information to the private sector.

Last, it is recommended to think beyond restoration to take stock of rapid propagation and limited funding. The diversity of land management options should be recognised and restoration should not be the only choice for all sites: regrowth and rotations, substitution by other crops (ideally indigenous and climate-resilient) to provide raw material to emerging value chains, or proper post-removal treatments could be part of the portfolio of options. Then decisions on which land management options to apply, and where, should be made according to scientifically robust evaluations that embrace a few dimensions: feasibility from both financial and legal perspectives, environmental (dis)services resulting from new land uses, and their contributions to local livelihoods. Besides, such land management options should explicitly integrate questions of benefit sharing and local employment (e.g. with manual operations) as well as specific inclusive models on community land to secure a “social license to operate”. Only such a diversified strategy might prove feasible and effective in the long-term to control alien tree invasions in South Africa; However, it would also require robust regulatory frameworks to avoid likely perverse effects, a necessary condition of its acceptability, and success.

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